

Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome
Clinical Research Programme

Household district	Study Number	Household Identification Number

CONSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE

1. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi (TENTACLE)

Statement by head of household:

Please circle Yes or No to confirm whether you agree or do not agree with each of the points below:

I have had the chance to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers that I have been given.	Yes / No
I agree to take part but I know that I can change my mind at a later date.	Yes / No
I agree that faecal samples can be collected by humans of the household to be submitted as part of the study.	Yes / No
I agree that faecal samples will be taken from humans of the household at three time points, Time point 0, Time point 1 (1 month after Time point 0, Time Point 2 (6 months after Time point 0)	Yes/ No
I have read the information sheet or it has been read to me.	Yes / No
I agree that faecal, blood and parasite samples can be collected from animals belonging to my household for the purpose of this study at Time Point 0, Time Point 1 and Time Point 2	Yes / No
I voluntarily agree to allow the household and the residents of the household to participate in the study.	Yes / No
I agree that samples from humans and animals of my household in which <i>E. coli</i> and non-typhoidal <i>Salmonella</i> , parasites or other zoonotic disease are found may be	Yes / No

Approved by
College of Medicine
02 MAY 2019
(COMREC)
Research and Ethics Committee

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shipped to the UK to undergo whole genome sequencing and further testing.	
I agree that samples from humans and animals of my household in which <i>E. coli</i> and non-typhoidal <i>Salmonella</i> , parasites or other zoonotic disease are found may be shipped to abroad to undergo whole genome sequencing and further testing.	Yes / No

Name of household owner	Date	Signature	Thumbprint
Impartial witness (if household owner has difficulty reading)	Date	Signature	Thumbprint
Staff obtaining consent	Date	Signature	Thumbprint

Physical address and contact details of PI:

Catherine Wilson

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THE COLLEGE OF MEDICINE
Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust
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Physical address and contact details of Ethics Committee:

Address: Private Bag 360, Blantyre

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Chichewa speaking contact:

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